

A Comparative Study on Tolerance Analysis Approaches

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A Comparative Study on TA Approaches

Outline

- Motivation – Geometric Variations Management as a Branch of Robust Design
- Proprietary Tolerance Analysis Approach
- The Concept of Skin Model Shapes and the Tolerance Analysis based thereon
- Case Studies: GD&T Standards and Assembly Sequence
- Conclusion and Outlook

insensitivity taguchi robust design methodology safety mean shift functional requirements
 geometric variations management variation disturbance dependability concept design
 noise factor FORM robustness process capability reliability
 availability simulation quality sensitivity analysis tolerance design
 six sigma SORM

Motivation

Geometric Variations Management as a Part of RD

Robust Design Methodology

Robust Design Methodology is understood as systematic efforts to achieve insensitivity to noise factors. These efforts are founded on an awareness of variation and can be applied in all stages of product design.

Ref.: Arvidsson&Gremyr2008, Reuter2000

Proprietary CAT software

Tolerance Analysis Approach

1. Definition of the assembly CAD models and specification of tolerance types and values as well as definition of their individual distributions.

1.

2. Definition of the assembly sequence (moves), the part/features relative positioning and the mating conditions (e. g. planar or cylindrical).

2.

3. Specification of Key Characteristics (KCs) and geometric functional requirements, such as gaps or clearances.

3.

5.

5. Analysis of the outcome data and identification of the main contributors to evaluate their sensitivity to the KCs and the tolerance design robustness. This step is supported by visualization techniques, such as histograms or KC plots.

Tolerance Representation for CAT

Consideration only of rotational and translational feature defects!

Simulation of the effect of part tolerances on KCs using a worst-case or statistical approach (methods such as Monte Carlo simulation are used) employing a tolerance simulation model.

Ref.: Prisco & Giorleo 2002, Shah et al. 2007, Mazur et al. 2011, Clozel et al. 2012

Skin Model Shapes

Fundamentals and Concept

GeoSpelling defines a **Specification** as a...

The Skin Model

Skin Model Shapes

- Skin Model is an Infinite Model
- No Possibility for Identification or Simulation
- Translation and Operationalization to a Finite Model

allocation of tolerances

Ref.: 2007Mathieu&Ballu, 2008Dantan,Ballu&Mathieu, 2011Ballu

Skin Model Shapes

Tolerance Analysis Approach

Case Study 1

Consideration of GD&T Standards

Quick View

Considered Geometric Deviations:

- Geometric Deviations are visible on the **Block**
 - Flatness, Parallelism & Position Tolerances
 - ft=fb=0.05, par=0.1, pos=0.2
 - Gaussian Distribution (Six Sigma)
- No Deviations of the **Plates**

Assembly Sequence:

- Straight 3-Point Moves
 - Block on first Plate
 - Plate on Block

Case Study 1

Consideration of GD&T Standards – Results

Findings

Mean Shift between the proprietary CAT tool and the approach based on SMS for dimensional FKCs

Prop. CAT tool overestimates the effects for the tilt angles

Case Study 2

Consideration of the Assembly Sequence

Quick View

Considered Geometric Deviations:

- Geometric Deviations are visible on the **first part (grey) and on the second part (blue)**
 - Flatness, Perpendicularity & Position Tolerances
 - $ft=fb=0.05$, $per=0.2$, $pos(A|B)=1.0$, $pos(C|D)=0.4$
 - Gaussian Distribution (Six Sigma)

Assembly Sequence:

- **Scenario 1:**
 - Primary contact (3 points) in the y-direction, secondary contact (2 points) in the x-direction
- **Scenario 2:**
 - Primary contact (3 points) in the x-direction, secondary contact (2 points) in the y-direction

Case Study 2

Consideration of the Assembly Sequence – Results

Findings

Mean Shift between the proprietary CAT tool and the approach based on SMS for dimensional FKCs

Little Effect of the Assembly Sequence on the minimal Gaps

Conclusion and Outlook

General Remarks and Further Research Challenges

Conclusion

- Qualitative comparison of the tolerance analysis approaches employing proprietary CAT tools and based on Skin Model Shapes
- Quantitative comparison of the approaches with two case studies
- Slight differences between the approaches can be observed
- Algorithms implemented in proprietary CAT tools are a black box

Outlook

- Integration of results obtained from computer aided manufacturing tools
- Consideration of various physical phenomena, such as gravity and friction
- In-depth analysis of the effects of various deviation parameters

Correlation length: 1

Correlation length: 5

Correlation length: 10

Summer School Tolerance Management

FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg, September 2015

2nd Summer School Tolerance Management at the KTmfk

- Exchange between Industry, Research and Students in Tolerance Management
- Three Day Programme with Industry Cases, Elevator-Pitches and Workshops
- September 2015 at the Chair of Engineering Design KTmfk, Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nürnberg

Topics:

- Methods and Tools for virtual Geometric Variations Management & RD
- Recent Trends in Research and Industry

Further Information:

- <http://www.mfk.fau.de/toleranzen>

